

EFFECTIVE TECHNIQUES IN TEACHING VOCABULARY TO YOUNG LEARNERS

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Annotation: *This article gives a brief overview of the advantages of using foreign language teaching techniques for young students, word memorization techniques, what resources they teach, and what other resources to use.*

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Today, one of the important factors in improving the quality of education is to increase the overall creativity of students. In this regard, the main priorities in increasing the creativity of primary school students are conscious teaching, the development of speech culture, the harmonization of written and oral exercises. In turn, working with dictionaries is one of the important factors in increasing creativity. Because working with dictionaries develops students' ability to observe, improves their speech culture, expands their thinking and worldview, increases vocabulary, improves students' writing skills. Linguistics studies all words in the language, their history, interpretation, spelling and other important issues. No language is relevant to society and cannot develop on its own outside of society. Language is, first of all, a means of interaction between society and people, so society is a direct link between people and the formation of language vocabulary. It is important to remember that language is important because it has the laws of the internal system of formation. Depending on the situation, a single idea in any developed language will be interpreted differently. Regardless of style, stylistic color, or situation, there are neutral words that are used in communication only for certain situations as the core of the language. We refer to this category of words in dictionaries as words of non-literary or non-standard vocabulary. Before looking at non-standard vocabulary, if we look at the problems with its style, it becomes clear that there are basically two different styles of use: functional and expressive. Functional style is interpreted as a specific, goal-oriented communication style specific to a certain group of people, i.e., for situations involving specific legal aspects of human movement, such as entrepreneurial style, verbal style, scientific style, etc. . Functional styles in modern languages are very complex and diverse. It should be noted that the method can be divided into written and oral forms, and can be divided into different forms for public use. But so far, linguists, although they have a lot of information, have not come to a consensus on the types of styles There are now many English resources available for teachers (tutors) and parents, but it is not possible to

cover everything. You need to choose what your students and you like. As one of these sources, I am in my teaching practice. I told him how to use it. By the way, there is a special section for English teachers and tutors. As for direct materials for teaching children, they are mainly provided in the form of video and audio materials. According to the search results within the site, the content for children is 412 files. These include songs, cartoons, lyrics and more. If it's an alphabet, it will be voiced, which is also very handy. Naturally, you need to have a tablet or laptop to work with this portal. When it comes to textbooks, books, and other educational publications, the opinions of different teachers sometimes differ. Again, this is from a personal experience. In rare cases, it is possible to work on only one textbook or series, the most correct is to create an individual program for each child, usually following a single clear scheme. For example: and video, audio, new words: colors, toys, personal pronouns, family and animal names are taken according to the Happy House system. We always give 2-4 minutes for the appropriate task in the lesson game. In English, but deliberately in the best interests of the child. One of my students loves dinosaurs, for which the additional tasks are worksheets in which you have to connect the dots in the correct alphabetical order, and so on. Giving your child assignments based on their interests and favorite characters will be more effective. Preschoolers love to play and it is best to learn English in a playful way. If you can instill a love for English right now, you are a great teacher because most people don't know the language that way, just because in school they have overcome all the desires for that language. As a serial, Happy House is very popular all over the world. I like that they have audio accompaniment to the lessons, very funny and catchy songs that the kids will remember quickly. And a very successful activity book. For example, the Task on Colors theme looks like this. The kids will be happy! For lessons on the subject of colors, I always use mine to combine my own and the material. Color cards are needed to get acquainted with colors, memorize them, and pronounce names. I use black and white for games. It all depends on your imagination. You can do this: first we will learn 6 colors. We give the child 6 felt-tip pens of the correct color and blank cards with balls, where everything is written only in words. You name the color in English, put the card on, and the child has to put a felt-tip pen of the desired color on it. When all 6 felt-tip pens are on the cards, give him 6 colored cards and he will check himself. No matter how many flowers you remember, always praise and say that the next time you will definitely be lucky. He also begins to visually memorize words and their meanings. Another of the most popular methods of teaching a foreign language is the use of information and communication methods such as computer technology, media, audio and others. The use of audio, video stories, fairy tales, cognitive materials in direct learning activities helps to individualize learning and develop motivation for preschool children's speaking activities. The use of ICT in direct foreign language learning activities develops two types of motivation: self-motivation when the proposed material is self-interesting and by showing the preschooler that he or she can understand it . the language he is learning. It brings satisfaction and gives them

confidence in their power and a desire to further improve.

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